

Research in Management and Humanities

DWIJMH VOL 1 NO 1 (2022), 22-40

Available online at www.dwijmh.org

Journal homepage: <http://www.dwijmh.org>

The Effect of Managerial Competencies on Employees' Trust in the Management

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 10 August 2022

Received in rev. form 12 September

2022 Accepted 05 December 2022

Keywords:

Management, Competencies, employee, Trust.

JEL Classification: M23; L15

ABSTRACT

Managerial competencies are seen these days as essential sources of attaining a competitive edge for all managerial levels from low, and middle up to senior managers. The study then aimed to determine the effect of managerial competencies on the employees' trust in management. To deepen the concept and establish the theories of the study, the literature was reviewed. Moreover, it used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design. The employees of Divine Word College of Laoag were the respondents, whereby questionnaires were used to gather the data. The study found that the managerial competencies of the administrators are not very high, and the employees' trust in management is not very high also. Pearson correlation indicates that there is a significant correlation between managerial competencies and the employees' trust in management.

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Introduction

In the era of globalization, many organizations face strong competition, and business survival has become one of the important management concerns. Business survival is not just a financial concern, but it is also a management and employment issue. Management and employees are contributing factors to organizational success. On one hand, management must have the capability to perform as expected to win the competition and lead the organization to success. On the other hand, management needs employees' cooperation to carry out their tasks. Employees' trust in management depends on many factors, and one of them is management competencies. Tzafirir, et al (2003) contended that managers' actions, behaviors, and procedures affect employees' trust in their managers, and losing this leads to low commitment and performance (Tan & Lim, 2009). This is supported by the study by Sharky (2009) that trust in leadership is vital for employee performance.

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Organizational failure is often attributed to the managers and leaders of an organization as Bangniyel (2012) explained in his book, the main cause of business failure is managerial incompetence. This is also caused by poor leadership as Sornum (2010) emphasized in his book that poor leadership can lead to organizational failure. These are why competent managers and leaders are needed in a competitive business environment today. They are not born but they are honed through experience, training, and education which emanated from knowledge and skills.

The institution, where the current researcher is connected, has gone through several transitions in management and leadership. This created setbacks in the workplace which prompted him to find out if managerial competency affects the employee's trust. Notably, no related research has been undertaken. Its output served as the basis for a human resource development plan, particularly on managerial competencies.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction that explains the rationale and the purpose of the study. The second part is the literature review which presents the related literature to deepen the understanding of the concepts and establish the theories that were the basis for the investigation. The third part is the research methodology which presents the research design, population of the study, its locale, data gathering procedures, ethical review, data gathering instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part presents the data gathered with analysis. The fifth part discusses its results corroborated with the reviewed literature.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the concepts of the study and establish theories that are the basis for the investigation. The literature reviewed was related to the current investigation. Thus, the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study is presented.

The Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Competency and Managerial Competency

Van der Klink & Boon, (2003), and Le Deist & Winterton, (2005) defined "competency" as a "fuzzy" concept that creates confusion because its sound is too close to competence. Some researchers have used the term interchangeably but lack an explanation (Moore et al., 2002; Vazirani, 2010). Merriam-Webster (n.d) defines competence as "the quality or the state of being competent" which means "having the requisites or adequate ability or qualities" or "having the capacity to function in a particular way". These definitions do not identify what the qualities or capacities are to be competent. Cambridge Dictionary (n.d) defines it as having "the ability to do well". This definition refers to competence as the ability to perform well in a particular task and it does not also identify what the abilities are to make a person competent. Sampson (1998) defines competence as "the ability to execute activities" and Saruchera (2022) defines it as "the ability to execute something successfully". While (Valyavskiy, et al., 2018) views it as "the ability to apply knowledge and skills". All these definitions refer to competence as the ability to apply or execute the job. While competency means "the possession of sufficient knowledge or skills" (Merriam-Webster, n.d). This definition does not tell us about the ability to perform but it is about the possession of knowledge or skills which is required to perform a task competently. Britannica Dictionary defines competency as "skills". Competencies are related to knowledge and skills which are required to perform competently. These are needed personal competencies for a person to perform a function (Hoyt, 1968). Concerning this concept, Hoffmann (1999) identified two meanings of the term "competency". The first refers to the outputs or results of training which is competent performance. The second refers to the inputs of the underlying attributes required for a person to attain competent performance. Hoffmann (1999) indicated that competency has several meanings depending on its purpose. The definition of Hoffmann (1999) implies that competency requires knowledge and skills which are prerequisites for competent performance (Pearson, 2010). The word was originally taken from the Latin word, "competentia" which "is authorized to judge" or "has the right to speak" (Caupin, et al. 2006, p. 9). However, McClelland (1973) views competency as "the underlying personality traits and enduring qualitative behaviors. McClelland's (1973) study found that poor students were also doing good as top students in the classroom. He concluded that traditional intelligence is less accurate in predicting job performance and success in life. He further pointed out that aside from traditional cognitive skills and knowledge,

personality variables predict job performance in the workplace. Similarly, Spencer & Spencer (1993) define competency as "motives, traits, self-concepts, attitudes or values, content knowledge, and behavioral skills that affect job performance". Page & Wilson (1994) likewise define competency as "the skills, abilities, and personal characteristics needed by a 'successful' or 'superior' manager".

In a nutshell, managerial competency refers to the possession of knowledge, skills, behavior, attitude, or values that support the successful management of people. Woodruffe, (2006) defines it as "a set of employees' behavior that must be used for the position that the tasks arising from this position competently mastered." Woodruffe (2006) identified several competencies that a manager must possess to perform such as the possession of knowledge, skills, and abilities, being motivated, and being willing to spend the necessary energy in a business environment.

The two definitions classify managerial competencies into two categories which are threshold competencies and performance competencies. Threshold competencies refer to the knowledge and skills required to perform a task. Performance competencies refer to behavior or commitment to achieving high performance (Krajcovicova, et.al. 2012). As a manager, one should have the basic knowledge and skills to perform the job and the motivation or behavior that leads to the achievement of organizational goals. Krajcovicova, et.al. (2012).

Dimensions of Managerial Competencies in the Context of Educational Institution

Banking industries have other different competency requirements such as knowledge of the organization, operational function, products and services, business markets, business process design, process management, interpersonal relationships, effective communications, leadership, customer service management, financial services industry, regulatory environment - financial services, etc. (IBM, 2020). Manufacturing industries might require different competencies to be effective and competent managers like people skills, interpersonal skills, communication, conflict resolution, having difficult conversations, managing up, change management, coaching and performance management and development, project management, self-management, time management, and scheduling, leadership, innovation, lean manufacturing (Cleary & Vickers, 2014). Since the context of the current study is an educational institution, the managerial competencies provided by Sherman, et al. (2002) might be appropriate. He identified seven managerial competencies namely, leadership skills, instructional leadership, resource management and allocation, human resource management, professional development practices, and community collaboration.

1. Leadership Skills

According to Gallup research as cited by Landry (2018) that 24 percent of employees are disengaged because of flawed leadership which leads to a decrease in productivity and profit. Such research indicates that effective leadership is needed and Landry (2018) identified several characteristics: the ability to influence, transparency, encouraging risk-taking and innovation, valuing ethics and integrity, decisiveness, and balancing hard truth with optimism. Sherman, et al. (2002) also identified several characteristics of good leadership, such as promoting ethical conduct, practicing participatory management, seeking feedback from subordinates, listening attentively, demonstrating fairness and consistency, conveying information fully, allowing employees to present issues and discuss issues together, promoting innovation, staying current on trends and issues, and disseminating information to the community about issues that are affecting the organization.

2. Instructional Leadership

Good and Clarke (2017), defined instructional leadership as "the ability to involve colleagues collaboratively in mutual learning and development, with the main purpose of improving teaching and learning". This definition emphasizes collaboration as a tool to improve learning and teaching. Grogan and Shakeshaft (2011) defined instructional leadership as "the ability to promote learning above all else for students and professional development for teachers to improve teaching efficiency". The definition identifies the essential responsibility of school leaders such as promoting learning and developing faculty to improve teaching efficiency. In addition, Dunkle, (2012) identifies the duties of principals such as describing a vision for academic success, creating a culture and climate that support students and

adult learning, using data to measure the progress of students and adults, and discovering and supporting talents that benefit the organization.

3. Resource Management and Allocation

Sherman, et al. (2002) asserted that management must ensure that expenditures are allowable and appropriate and that they are available throughout the fiscal year. Funds are to be allocated equitably to effective programs and sites based on such indicators as attendance, retention, student outcomes, and benchmarks. He further stated that resources are used to integrate and upgrade technology and to provide professional development on the effective use of technology for management and administrators.

4. Human Resource Management

Human resource management is one of the key components of managerial competency. This is a crucial component that determines the competitiveness of a business organization. According to Armstrong, (2016, p.7), human resource management is "a strategic, integrated, and coherent approach to the employment, development, and well-being of the people working in organizations". This definition emphasizes two important responsibilities of human resources: human development and well-being. Boxall and Purcell, (2016:7) define human resource management as "the process through which management builds the workforce and tries to create the human performances that the organization needs". Sherman (2002) indicated that human resource managers must provide a formal orientation of new staff and learners to the adult education program, and provide for a system of management observations and evaluations focusing on such areas as (1) organizing and delivering instruction, (2) managing instructional resources, (3) monitoring and assessing progress, (4) accommodating diverse learning styles, (5) using materials and technology, (6) providing learner guidance and referrals, and (7) helping learners transfer learning to real-life situations.

Professional Development

New knowledge and new technology continue to develop because of discoveries. The increase in the use of information and communications technologies entails increased demands on the competencies of managers and employees. For example, teachers must be updated regularly to be informed of what is going on in the world and enhance their job performance through continuous professional development (Mizell, 2010). They must continually expand their knowledge and skills to implement the best educational practices (Mizell, 2010). The results of different studies centered on the same finding that teaching quality and good school leadership are contributing factors to students' academic achievement. Concerning professional development, Sherman (2002) clarified that school leaders must be updated with research on instructional practices, management, and leadership, as well as on effective practices in professional development. These are to be shared with staff and engage teachers in a variety of activities that foster their learning such as participating in collegial networking and subscribing to journals. Further, Sherman (2002) suggested that school leaders must support the professional development of management through stipends, by providing release time, and by engaging in professional development activities that focus on student and program improvement. It is also recommended that management must be involved in the identification and planning of their professional development activities, such as inquiry research, workshops, institutes, and observation/feedback (Sherman, 2002).

5. Community Collaboration.

The educational institution does not exist in isolation from the community. The school is part of the community, therefore community involvement in its governance is a must. Spillane & Seashore Louis, (2002) mentioned that collaboration is at the heart of school improvement initiatives and subsequently requires interactions among the components. The collaborative approach is a new direction for school improvement ((Barth, 1990; Cook & Friend, 1992; Fullan, 1993, Welch, 1998) and shared governance is one of the requirements to strengthen collaboration. Specifically, the school involves teachers in decision-making and accommodates the opinion of the parents. Sherman, et al. (2002) suggest though, that beyond shared decision-making, the school needs to establish partnerships and alliances with businesses, institutions of higher learning, local educational agencies, child care centers, health centers, employment and job training centers, boards, and other agencies to expand understanding of adult education, assess

needs, enhance program resources, and improve services for adult learners. Sherman, et al (2002) also added that as part of community collaboration, the school needs to maintain ongoing agency outreach, publicity, staff funding, community expertise, equipment, and other resources.

Employees' Trust in the Management

Organizational success will depend on many factors that have a direct relationship with organizational life. It does not solely depend on sufficient financial capital, but also human capital. High-quality workplace relationships affect the job performance of employees which contributes to organizational performance (Tran, et al. 2018). His study emphasized that workplace relationship has been playing important role in employees' well-being and performance rating at work (Tran, et al. 2018). A similar finding was also presented in the study of El-Said and Shaaban (2014) that workplace relationships affect productivity. One of the important factors that influence workplace relationships is trust. Merriam-Webster (n.d) defines it as "assured reliance on the character, ability, strength, or truth of someone or something" or "one in which confidence is placed". This emphasizes the reliance of someone on someone else in whom the confidence is placed. This is similar to the definition given by the Cambridge Dictionary (n.d) which defines trust as "to believe that someone is good and honest and will not harm you, or that something is safe and reliable". Rotter (1967) defines trust as "An expectancy held by an individual or a group that the word, promise, or verbal or written statement of another individual or group can be relied on". Driscoll, (1978) defines it as "the belief that the decision-makers will produce outcomes favorable to the person's interests without any influence by the person". Larzelere & Huston, (1980) defined it as "the extent to which a person believes another person (or persons) to be benevolent and honest". When there is high-quality trust among employees and management, it creates collective trust. Collective trust (Bucero, 2012) contributes to the organizational environment. It influences the positive atmosphere in which each member trusts each other and feels comfortable dealing with each other and allows open communication and within such an environment, decisions are made collectively (Holm & Nystedt, 2010). Bauer, et al. (2019) argued that individuals with a high level of generalized trust are more likely to cooperate across a wide variety of situations. This is confirmed by the study by Doyle (2021) that cultural trust affects cooperation.

Trust between employees and management is another issue in the organization. Mary Parker Follett defines management as doing things through other people or getting things done through other people (Britanica, 2021). This definition is often criticized for not highlighting how the management gets things done through other people. However, it remains valid. This suggests that employees must trust management to carry out their responsibilities. For example, a study shows that employees' trust in management and supervisors has a positive impact on positive attitudes and behaviors (Shah, 2014 Brown, et al. (2015) likewise found a positive relationship between employees' trust and workplace performance, in three aspects namely, financial performance, labor productivity, and service quality. It is along this line, that Snow (1997) and Serrat (2017) suggested that management needs to build trust in the workplace. Serrat (2017) recommends several factors that management needs to do to develop the trust of employees toward management such as presenting a clear and attainable vision to the employees, living the values of the organization through their own lives, establishing an atmosphere of trust in the organization, decisions must be based on factual and objective data, and compensation must be based on merits.

Seok, et al. (2015) have also identified three dimensions of trust of employees toward the management namely trust in management competency, trust in management integrity, and trust in the working relationship. Trust in management competency refers to employees' trust in management's ability to carry out their tasks. Employees' trust in management integrity means that employees believe that the management is honest and trustworthy. Meanwhile, working relationship refers to the knowledge of management about their employees, their backgrounds, and inviting them to discuss work-related problems together.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002) and Seok, et al. (2015)

Figure 1: The framework reflects the relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management. It depicts the effect of managerial competencies on the employees' trust in management.

Statement of the Problems

The study examined the effect of managerial competencies on employees' trust in management. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

- 1 What are the managerial competencies of administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of:
 - a. Leadership skills
 - b. Resource management allocation
 - c. Human resource management
 - d. Professional development
 - e. community collaboration
2. What is the employees' trust in management in terms of:
 - a. Trust in management competencies
 - b. Trust in management integrity
 - c. Working relationship
3. Is there a relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management?

Assumption

The study assumed that managerial competencies influence employees' trust in management and that both can be measured.

Hypothesis

Studies have found the effect of managerial competencies on business performance (Ncube & Chimucheka, 2019, Veliu & Manxhari, 2017), and employee engagement (Unnikrishnan, 2020). The current study hypothesized that managerial competencies affect employees' trust in management.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the study is the Divine Word College of Laoag employees and administrators. It delimits its investigation on several dimensions of managerial competencies and employees' trust in management.

Research Methodology

Scientific research involves procedures and techniques that are used to carry out the study scientifically. The research methodology determines the quality and reliability of the study (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). This was carried out through appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Since the study is quantitative research, it used descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of the leadership competency of administrators and its effect on the work engagement of employees. The use of descriptive research is to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and tabulated through statistical methods. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes “what is” about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

In line with the current study, the descriptive assessment and correlational method were deployed. The study determined the level of leadership competency and its effect on work engagement.

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges of Laoag, Laoag City, Ilocos Norte

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees and faculty of Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte. The total enumeration sampling was used, and 276 employees were taken as respondents.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires by Sherman, et al. (2002) on managerial competencies and Seok, et al. (2015) on employees’ trust in management

Data Gathering Procedures

In the data gathering process, the researcher sent a letter to the president of the College, requesting him to allow the researcher to survey the college. The researcher personally met the employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires.

The questionnaires were retrieved from the employees’ representatives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Congruent to the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design, descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of the different managerial competencies and employees’ trust in management and Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between managerial competency and the employees’ trust in management.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation were used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very high</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents data that was gathered through research questionnaires. The data are presented in different tables and arranged according to the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What are the managerial competencies of administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of:

- a. Leadership skills
- b. Resource management allocation
- c. Human resource management
- d. Professional development
- e. community collaboration
- f.

Table 1. Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Leadership Skills.

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. Engages in and promotes ethical conduct.	3.63	A
2. Uses and practices a participatory management style open to constructive criticism.	3.56	A
3. Seeks input from all levels of staff, listens attentively, demonstrates fairness and consistency, and conveys information fully.	3.53	A
4. Uses a variety of modes of communication.	3.59	A
5. Encourages and allows the opportunity for staff to confer and present issues and problems affecting instruction and other program-related services.	3.48	A
6. Supports innovative practices to improve program-related issues and services	3.54	A
7. Provides opportunities for learners, management, and community stakeholders to give feedback before significant program changes are implemented.	3.49	A
8. Delegates authority and decision-making to appropriate entities and supports their decisions.	3.52	A
9. Uses collaborative teams and other strategies to identify outcomes, design curriculum, share instructional strategies, conduct assessments, analyze results, and adjust instructional processes.	3.49	A
10. Present innovations to appropriate staff and make decisions that are aligned with their feedback.	3.49	A
11. Disseminates information in the community about program accomplishments through the use of technology and other means.	3.58	A
Composite Mean	3.54	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/Very high*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

The data reveals that the managerial competencies of administrators along with leadership skills obtained a composite mean of 3.54 which is referring to "agree or high". This suggests that the employees agree that the administrators of the institution behaved ethically, practiced participatory management, supported innovation, provide feedback mechanisms, delegated authority, and disseminated information concerning the development of the institution. This positive evaluation indicates that the administrators are competent in terms of leadership skills. The favorable leadership practice needs to be sustained because it can affect individual and organizational performance as indicated by many studies such as Nedovic, et al., (2013), Ariussanto, et. al., (2020), Khan, et.al., (2020), and Rohana and Abdullah (2017).

Table 2. Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Resource Management Allocation.

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. Ensures that expenditures are allowable and appropriate and that allocated funds are available throughout the fiscal year.	3.51	A
2. Evidence: - Allocates funds equitably to effective programs and sites based on such indicators as attendance, retention, student outcomes, and benchmarks.	3.49	A
3. Uses resources to integrate and upgrade technology and provides professional development on effective use of technology for management and administrators.	3.48	A
Composite Mean	3.49	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

The managerial competency of administrators in terms of resource management allocation gained a composite mean of 3.49 which is understood as "agree or high". The employees agree (3.49) that the administrators allocated funds for different programs and used resources to upgrade technologies and professional development. This evaluation implies that the management recognized the importance of providing budget allocation for different programs because, without it, the objective of the institution cannot be achieved. This favorable practice has been recommended by Gitau, et al. (2020) and Gregoriev and Modrus (2022) for organizational and academic performance.

Table 3. Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Human Resource Management

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. Provides formal orientation of new staff and learners to the adult education program.	3.53	A
2. Provides for a system of management observations and evaluations focusing on such areas as (1) organizing and delivering instruction, (2) managing instructional resources, (3) monitoring and assessing progress, (4) accommodating diverse learning styles, (5) using materials and technology, (6) providing learner guidance and referrals, and (7) helping learners transfer learning to real-life situations.	3.51	A
3. Recognizes when staff members are not performing effectively, provides guidance and support to enable attainment of needed competencies, involves appropriate stakeholders, and follows required procedures and due process, leading to staff termination when necessary	3.47	A
4. Fulfills legal or program requirements for compliance, record keeping, and reporting.	3.54	A
5. Maintains confidentiality and limits access to staff and learner files and records (e.g. past education, employment, interests, disabilities).	3.53	A
6. Ensures data are accessible, promptly, to staff, learners, community members, and other stakeholders (via such means as reports, use of media, and web pages).	3.52	A
Composite Mean	3.51	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

The data disclosed that the managerial competency of administrators along with human resource management gained a composite mean of 3.51 which is also interpreted as "agree or high". In this regard, the employees agree that the administrators or the management have practiced principles of human resource management. The administrators, to a high degree, conducted orientation for the new staff and learners, provided a system of management observation and evaluation, and support for staff development, fulfilled legal requirements and, maintained the confidentiality of sensitive records, and transparency at the same time. Good human resource management has been considered very important in any organization because it affects the performance of any organization as proven by Rana and Malik (2017), Lambooi, et al. (2006), Rasool, et al., and (2019), Vermeeren, et al. (2014).

Table 4. Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Professional Development Practices

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. Keeps up-to-date with research on instructional practices, management, and leadership, as well as on effective practices in professional development, and shares those practices with staff.	3.49	A
2. Engages in a variety of activities that foster own learning such as participating in collegial networking and subscribing to journals.	3.42	A
3. Supports the professional development of management by stipends, or other types of support enabling management to relay specific information about professional development opportunities by providing release time, and engaging in professional development activities that focus on student and program improvement.	3.42	A

4. Encourages management to become involved in the identification and planning of their professional development and to engage in a variety of activities including inquiry research, workshops, institutes, and observation/feedback (e.g., peer coaching and mentoring).	3.48	A
5. Designs collaboratively, a staff development program based on the results of staff needs assessments, informal conversations, identified state or local needs and mandates, and research.	3.49	A
6. Supports a variety of professional development activities that reflect the organization's mission and principles of adult learning.	3.49	A
7. Acquires and maintains knowledge of technology and applies it to adult learning and professional development.	3.5	A
8. Shares information on providing training in and promoting the use of technology with management and other staff	3.51	A
Composite Mean	3.48	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

The managerial competency of administrators concerning professional development practice obtained a composite mean of 3.48 which means “agree or high”. The employees agree that the administrators have given attention to the professional development of staff or faculty along with the latest technology or knowledge. Professional development has been considered an important element in human resource practice because knowledge and technology related to the different fields of life are constantly changing and the organization and employees must adapt to its external environment. Failing to adapt to the new changes in the environment can hamper the performance of an organization. It has been indicated by several research works that professional development contributes to organizational performance (Jacobs & Washington, 2003, Puteh, 2017, Vinesh, 2014, Ntadom, et al. 2021).

Table 5. Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Community Collaboration

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. Maintains ongoing agency outreach, publicity, and staff funding, community expertise, equipment, and other resources.	3.46	A
2. Establishes partnerships and alliances with businesses, institutions of higher learning, local educational agencies, child care centers, health centers, employment and job training centers, boards, and other agencies to expand understanding of adult education, assess needs, enhance program resources, and improve services for the adult learner.	3.48	A
Composite Mean	3.47	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

The data presents the managerial competencies of administrators along with community collaboration with a composite mean of 3.47, considered as “agree or high”. It means that employees confirm that the administrators maintain an office for outreach with its necessary resources and establish partnerships with different agencies. Kidd, et al (2021) argued that community partnership can provide students with better education and access to resources that can help them succeed in school. Judith, et al. (2015) emphasized further that school-community partnership plays an important role in a successful school because through collaboration resources and support for staff's and student's needs can be provided.

Table 6. Summary: Managerial Competencies of Administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag

ITEMS	Mean	DI
1. Leadership Skills	3.54	A
2. Resource Management Allocation	3.49	A
2. Human Resource Management	3.51	A
3. Professional Development	3.48	A
4. Community Collaboration	3.47	A
Overall Mean	3.50	A

Source: Sherman, et al. (2002).

In summary, the managerial competencies of administrators in terms of leadership skills, resource management

allocation, human resource management, professional development, and community collaboration obtained an overall mean rating of 3.50 which is considered “agree or high”. The employees agree that the administrators are competent to a high degree. It shows that there is room for improvement in different areas indicated in the study. The management needs to review and improve their practices as these have impacts on the performance of the institution. Furthermore, studies corroborate to such claim that managerial competencies influence the performance of educational institutions (Hawi, et al, 2015, Ncube & Chimucheka, 2019, Masoud & Al khateeb, 2020)

Problem 2: What is the employees’ trust in management in terms of:

a. *Trust in management competencies*

b. *Trust in management integrity*

c. *Working relationship*

Table 7. Employees’ Trust in Management in terms of Trust in Management Competencies

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. My head of department shows confidence in task performance and administration.	3.49	A
2. The ability of my department head is undeniable.	3.42	A
3. My department head brings development to the department.	3.36	SWA
4. I have confidence in the ability of my department head.	3.46	A
5. My department head is my source of reference.	3.40	SWA
6. My department head can make quick decisions.	3.37	SWA
7. My department head is good at administration.	3.42	A
8. My department head has a convincing appearance.	3.41	A
9. My department head has great experience in performing his/her tasks.	3.39	SWA
10. My department head is capable of delegating tasks to his/her employees.	3.43	A
Composite Mean	3.42	A

Source: Seok, et al. (2015)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/Very high*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

The employees’ trust in management in terms of management competency gained a composite mean of 3.42 which is interpreted as “agree or high”. This means that the employees trust the management’s efficient delivery to a high degree. Rooms for improvement, however, are deeply encouraged. Studies suggest that the trust of employees in management can also affect the satisfaction and affective commitment of employees toward their job (Jiang & Probst, 2016). This, in turn, consequently decreases their performance (Mayer & Gavin, 2005). Hence, the top management may explore assigning competent people to key positions for leverage. The result of several studies showed that possessing managerial competencies can affect organizational performance (Hawi, et al. 2015, Ncube & Chimucheka, 2015, Masoud & Al khateeb, 2020, Alebiosu, et al, 2022).

Table 8. Employees’ Trust in Management in terms of Trust in Management Integrity

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. My department head is very sincere in performing tasks and in making decisions for the department.	3.64	A
2. My department head is a disciplined person in task performance and administration.	3.61	A
3. I like the ethical values of my head of department.	3.64	A
4. My head of department has high integrity.	3.63	A
5. My head of department always shows a good example to his/her employees	3.65	A
6. My department head is a person with high principles	3.62	A

7. The management of my department head is honest and truthful.	3.63	A
8. My department head respects his/her employees.	3.64	A
Composite Mean	3.63	A

Source: Seok, et al. (2015)

The employees' trust in management concerning management integrity received a composite mean of 3.63 which is considered "agree or high". Though it is not very high, the employees somehow trust that management is sincere, honest, behaves ethically, and has moral principles, and integrity. The study of Engelbrecht, et al. (2017) claims that the trust of employees in ethical leadership affects to a certain degree of employees' commitment toward their work.

Table 9. Employees' Trust in Management in terms of Working Relationship

INDICATORS	Mean	DI.
1. My department head has good knowledge of my background	3.63	A
2. My department head spends time with his/her/her employees	3.61	A
3. My department head understands me well	3.60	A
4. My department head always discusses work-related issues with his/her employees.	3.59	A
Composite Mean	3.61	A

Source: Seok, et al. (2015)

As shown, the data in the table demonstrates that the employees' trust in management in terms of working relationships obtained a composite mean of 3.61 which means "agree or high". This evaluation specifies that to a high degree, the employees trust the management in managing the working relationship. There is a good working relationship between the supervisors and the subordinates. The management may look closely into this because working relationship affects employees' satisfaction, performance, and organizational performance (Raza, et al. (2015, Occhipinti, et al. 2018, Golden & Veiga, 2008).

Table 10. Summary of Employees' Trust in Management

ITEMS	Mean	DI
1. Trust in Management Competencies	3.42	A
2. Trust in Management Integrity	3.63	A
3. Work Relationship	3.61	A
Overall Mean	3.55	A

Source: Seok, et al. (2015)

The summary table displays that overall the employees' trust in management along with management competencies, management integrity, and working relationship obtained an overall mean rating of 3.55 which is still considered "agree or high". Since the result is not very high, a recommendation is to fine-tune management competencies, management integrity, and work relationships to encourage employee engagement. This is pointed out by Jiang and Probst (2016) that managing employees' trust can help the organization avoid job insecurity and instead, create a more healthy work environment with highly engaged employees.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management?

Table 11. Relationship between Managerial Competencies and Employees' Trust In Management

		TMC	TMI	W
LS	Pearson Correlation	.659**	.687**	.704**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
RMA	Pearson Correlation	.727**	.705**	.710**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
HRM	Pearson Correlation	.758**	.763**	.751**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
PD	Pearson Correlation	.738**	.732**	.734**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
CC	Pearson Correlation	.678**	.638**	.628**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Software.

The result of the Pearson correlation shows that managerial competencies such as leadership skills, resource management allocation, human resource management, professional development, and community collaboration are all correlated with the employees' trust in management significantly at 0.01 level (2-tailed). This finding shows that enriching the managerial competencies unit will necessarily increase employees' trust in management. Doing well in leadership skills, resource allocation management, human resources management, professional development, and community collaboration can positively affect employees' trust in management, trust in competencies, integrity, and work relationship.

Result and Discussion

The focus of the study was to determine the effect of managerial competencies on the employees' trust in management. The study found the components of managerial competencies of administrators are considered high and the employees' trust in management is also. A significant correlation existed between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management. This result leads to a deeper discussion on the essence of managerial competencies and employees' trust in management.

The effect of management competencies on the employees' trust is supported by a neuroscience study. Zak (2017) researched the brain chemical oxytocin to develop a framework for creating a culture of trust and building a happier, more loyal, and more productive workplace. Zak (2017) observed people's oxytocin levels in response to various situations. There were eight management behaviors identified that stimulate oxytocin production and generate trust namely recognizing excellence, inducing "challenge stress", giving people discretion on how they do their work, enabling job crafting, sharing information broadly, intentionally building a relationship, facilitating whole-person growth, and showing vulnerability. From this finding, it is conclusive that building trust can be done by setting a clear direction, giving people autonomy on how they do their things, building good work relationships, and helping employees to grow. The finding of the current study is supported by the neuroscience study (Zak, 2017) which suggests that building employees' trust in management can be done through professional development, positive work relationships, good human resource management practice, good leadership that provides clear direction, and resource allocation management.

Building employees' trust in management must be one of the management's concerns as this let them get engaged in their jobs and make them more loyal and satisfied (Jiang & Probst, 2016). Consequently, satisfied employees and engaged employees increase productivity levels which translates into work performance and organizational performance (Mayer & Gavin, 2005, Dirks & Ferrin, 2001, Li & Yan, 2009, Radomska, et al, 2019). When there is trust between employees and management, cooperation and participation are easier, and work or projects can be easily carried out (Radomska, et al., 2019). On the contrary, when there is a lack of trust, the employees quit their job (Erkilic, et al., 2019) in an unhealthy workplace (Smith, 2019).

The current study contributes to a deeper discussion on trust management. Building the trust of employees in management takes not only requiring moral integrity and honesty, but also takes a different aspect of management and leadership. It suggests that the primary concern of the management is building employees' trust to achieve its objectives. It is then recommended to conduct another future study and include a different aspect of management and its effect on employees' trust in management.

Conclusion

The study determined the effect of managerial competencies on the employees' trust in management. The result indicates that all the dimensions under managerial competencies are evaluated high and the employees' trust in management is also high. In terms of the correlation between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management shows a significant correlation. It concludes that managerial competencies affect the employees' trust in management. Any positive change in managerial competencies such as leadership skills, resource management allocation, human resources management, professional development, and community collaboration, can affect the trust of employees in management.

Authors Contribution: Conceptualization: D.A. A.P.B. Methodology: D.A. J.R.L. C.P.S. Data collection: A.P.B. J.R.L. C.P.S. M.J.E. Formal Analysis: D.A., M.J.E. Writing-Review and Editing: D.A. M.J.E.

All authors have read and agreed to the published final version of the manuscript

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, due to the research does not deal with vulnerable groups or sensitive issues.

Data Availability Statement: the data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. Data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

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